

DIAGNOSIS OF CYSTIC FIBROSIS IN CHILDREN**(clinical case)****M. Mukhitdinova**

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Summary

Cystic fibrosis is a very complex genetic pathology characterized by multiple organ and polysystem lesions of the body. A timely integrated approach to the diagnosis of the disease contributes to early diagnosis and the initiation of targeted therapy, which is the main condition for achieving positive dynamics of cystic fibrosis and improving the quality of life of every patient suffering from this pathology.

Key words: cystic fibrosis, pulmonary-intestinal form, child, complete blood count, biochemical blood test, sweat test.

Relevance. Of particular concern to modern researchers is exocrine genetic pathology - cystic fibrosis (cystic fibrosis of the pancreas, Landsteiner-Fanconi disease) [2,7], inherited in an autosomal recessive manner and manifested by early clinical manifestations in the form of damage to the respiratory system, gastrointestinal tract, and also other organs [1,4,8].

The incidence of this pathology throughout the world varies from 1 in 377 cases among newborns [1,3], despite the fact that females, compared to males, more often suffer from the pulmonary form, and have a younger age at the time of death [5, 10].

The average age of patients with cystic fibrosis varies in different countries of the world and depends on the state of timely screening diagnosis [9]. At the same time, the development and application of new methods for treating cystic fibrosis over the past decade has significantly improved the prognosis of the disease, increasing both the life expectancy of patients and its quality [6,8].

Material and research methods. The clinical material for the study was child I., 1 year 5 months old, admitted on December 6, 2021 for inpatient examination and treatment at the Republican Scientific and Practical Medical Center (Uzbekistan, Tashkent) with a diagnosis of cystic fibrosis pulmonary form E84.0.

Research methods included general clinical, laboratory (complete blood count (CBC), biochemical blood test (BAC), coagulogram, general urine test (UCA), general stool test (FCA), sweat analysis, throat smear examination) and instrumental examination (MSCT of the chest).

Results and discussion. Child I., (gender - male), born in 2020, lives in the Surkhandarya region, was admitted to the pulmonology department of the Republican Scientific and Practical Medical Center of Pediatrics on December 6, 2021 with complaints from the mother about a change in voice, difficulty breathing, cough, increased body temperature to 38.0 C, general weakness, loss of appetite, increased breathing, changes in the shape of the chest, frequent colds.

From the life history, the child was born from healthy parents at term, without complications from the second pregnancy during the second physiological birth, with a body weight of 3800 g and a height of 50 cm, he cried immediately. The mother's pregnancy occurred against the background of anemia, acute respiratory infections and toxicosis. Hereditary history is not burdened.

The early neonatal period was uneventful. On the 5th day of life, the child was discharged under the supervision of a local pediatrician.

According to the mother, the child fell ill 1.5 months ago. The disease began with signs of obstruction, cough, and increased body temperature to 38.0C. In connection with this, they consulted a doctor at their place of residence, where they prescribed outpatient treatment for acute respiratory infections. Due to the lack of effect, the child was hospitalized for inpatient treatment at his place of residence where a diagnosis of pneumonia was established. The treatment did not lead to an improvement in the child's general condition, and with the above complaints they contacted the clinic of the Russian National Medical Research Center for Pediatrics.

Upon objective examination, the general condition of the child upon admission to the Republican Scientific and Medical Center is severe, the skin and visible mucous membranes are clean, the pharynx is hyperemic, and the tonsils are enlarged. Breathing through the nose and mouth, with the participation of additional pectoral muscles, the anteroposterior size of the chest is increased, retraction of the lower intercostal muscles is noted. During auscultation in the lungs, against the background of hard breathing, dry and moist rales are heard throughout the lung on both sides. Heart sounds are muffled, the pulse is rhythmic, the boundaries are within normal limits. The abdomen is somewhat distended due to flatulence, stool and urine output are regular.

Laboratory parameters: In the general blood test (CBC) dated December 7, 2021: hemoglobin (HB) – 106.0 g/l [M: 130-160 g/l; F: 120-140 g/l], red blood cells (RDC) – $3.9 \times 10^{12}/l$ [M: $4.0-5.0 \times 10^{12}/l$; F: $3.9-4.7 \times 10^{12}/l$], color index – 0.8 [0.85-1.05], mean erythrocyte volume (MCV) – $79.9 \mu m^3$ [80-100 μm^3], hemoglobin content in one erythrocyte (MCH) – 26.7 pg [30 -35 pg], erythrocyte hemoglobin concentration (MCHC) - 334 g/l [320-360 g/l], erythrocyte anisocytosis rate - 15.1% [11.5-14.5%], hematocrit (HCT) - 31.6% [M: 35 -49%; F: 32-45%], platelets (PLT) – $507.0 \times 10^9/l$ [180-320 $\times 10^9/l$], mean platelet volume (MPV) – $7.7 \mu m^3$ [3.6-9.4 μm^3], platelet anisocytosis index (PDW) – 15.3% [1-20%], thrombocrit (PCT) – 0.39% - [0.15-0.45%], leukocytes (WBC) – $11.2 \times 10^9/l$ [4.0-9.0 $\times 10^9/l$], segmented neutrophils – 32.1% [47-72%], eosinophils – 1.0% [0.5-5.0%], basophils – 0.2% [0-1.0%], monocytes – 3.9% [3-11%], lymphocytes – 62.8% [19-37%] , erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR) - 7 mm/hour [M: 2-10 mm/hour; F:2-15 mm/h].

In the biochemical blood test dated December 7, 2021: total protein - 69.0 g/l [66-85 g/l], albumin - 38.0 g/l - [35-55 g/l], glucose - 2.1 mmol/l [3.2-6.1 $\mu mol/l$], total bilirubin – 9.3 $\mu mol/l$ - [3.4-20.5 $\mu mol/l$], bound bilirubin – 2.3 $\mu mol/l$ [0.86-5.3 $\mu mol/l$], free bilirubin – 7.0 $\mu mol/l$ [1.7 -17.1 $\mu mol/l$], ALT – 40.0 U/d [<40 U/l], AST – 52.0 U/d [<35 U/l], alkaline phosphatase – 200.0 U/d [<15 years - <644 U /l, 15-17 years <483 U/l].

In the coagulogram dated December 7, 2021: prothrombin time (PTT) - 12 sec, PTI - 94% [14-19%], INR - 1.02 sec [0.85-1.15], activated partial thromboplastin time (APTT) - 29.0 sec [23-36 sec], thrombin time (TV) – 17.0 sec - [up to 30 sec], fibrinogen – 3.8 g/l [2-4 g/l], recalcification time - 130 sec [60-120 sec], thrombotest - IV stage [IV-VI stage], ethanol test - negative [negative].

Study of the secretion of the sweat glands (sweat test) from December 11, 2021: sweat chlorides - 122 mmol/l (<60 mmol/l).

Examination of a throat smear dated December 11, 2021: Klebsiella spp (moderate growth) isolated.

In the general urine analysis dated 12/07/2021: quantity - 50 ml, color - light yellow, transparency - slightly cloudy, relative density -1018, reaction - acidic, protein - absent, epithelium: squamous - 0-1, leukocytes - 0 -1, salts – urates.

In the general analysis of stool dated December 7, 2021: shape – mushy, color – yellow-green with the presence of neutral fats “++”, fatty acids – “+”, soap – “+”, starch – “+”, mucus – “+”, leukocytes - 1-2.

Instrumental study: MSCT dated December 8, 2021: signs of prolonged interstitial polysegmental pneumonia on both sides against the background of fibrotic changes.

Thus, in patient I., at the age of 1 year ... month, as a result of clinical and laboratory-instrumental studies, specific changes characteristic of pulmonary intestinal cystic fibrosis were revealed. In this connection, the final diagnosis was established: Cystic fibrosis mixed form (pulmonary-intestinal) E84.8.

After the final diagnosis was established, therapy was started taking into account clinical recommendations for the management of patients with cystic fibrosis: cefepime 300 mg x 2 times/day IM for 7 days, Ambrobene 1.0 x 2 times/day IV for 7 days, aprostad 10 thousand units. + sodium chloride solution 0.9% - 50.0 ml IV drip for 3 days, dexamethasone 1.0 ml + sodium chloride solution 0.9% - 5.0 ml IV drip for 5 days, aminophylline solution 2.4% - 0.5 ml IV for 3 days, polyoxidonium 2.0 IV for 5 days, Sermin solution IV drip for 3 days, Lecorn 2.0 IV slowly for 3 days, Creon 1 capsule 3 times a day during.

With positive dynamics, the child was discharged under the supervision of a local pediatrician at his place of residence with recommendations: limiting the consumption of easily digestible carbohydrates; avoid hypothermia, contact with colds and infectious patients (ARVI, acute respiratory infections); chest massage daily at home; continue taking the enzyme preparation Creon - 10,000 IU, 1 capsule 3 times a day, Ursosan 250

mg per day, vitamin preparations (Aevit 1 capsule 1 time per day, Aquadetrim 6 drops (30 thousand units) 1 time per day, immunozinc 1 tablet 1 time per day, folic acid 1 mg 1 time per day), Elcar 8 drops 2 times per day for 1 month; control of blood, urine, and feces tests after 1 month.

Conclusion. Cystic fibrosis is a very complex genetic pathology, characterized by multi-organ and multi-system damage to the body [1,6,10]. A timely integrated approach to diagnosing the disease contributes to early diagnosis and initiation of targeted therapy, which is the main condition for achieving positive dynamics of cystic fibrosis and improving the quality of life of every patient suffering from this pathology.

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